

NUCLEATION AND PROPAGATION OF CRACKS DURING STRAIN CORROSION OF GRP

D. HULL and P. J. HOGG

*Department of Metallurgy and Materials Science
University of Liverpool
P. O. Box 147, Liverpool L69 3BX, U.K.*

ABSTRACT

The mechanisms of crack nucleation and propagation in $\pm 55^\circ$ angle ply sections of glass fibre polyester resin filament wound pipe tested in both stress and strain corrosion conditions have been studied using optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy. The failure processes are compared with similar tests in hoop wound pipe. Four distinct stages of deformation and fracture have been identified. Stress and strain corrosion failure is associated with fibre fracture and characteristic planar fracture surfaces are obtained. The main difference between $\pm 55^\circ$ sections and hoop wound sections is the occurrence of transverse cracking in the $\pm 55^\circ$ sections in the initial loading stage. These cracks allow acid to penetrate through the inner lamina and lead to an enhanced stress corrosion cracking effect. The results are interpreted in terms of the stress acting parallel and perpendicular to the fibres.

INTRODUCTION

Environmental testing of GRP has traditionally consisted of simple immersion of test samples, often at elevated temperatures, followed by static tests to determine the reduction in properties. This has proved adequate for service conditions in which the material is not subjected to any external loads. The degradation mechanisms which occur are dependent primarily on the resistance of the resin to the environmental conditions. Absorption of the environment may lead to resin plasticisation and swelling. In the case of water immersion, subsequent shrinkage of the resin and debonding of the fibres may occur [1]. Fibre degradation may occur at a later stage.

GRP shows good chemical resistance and retention of properties if a suitable glass resin combination is used. Norwood and Fairbrother [2] report negligible reductions in strength and modulus for chopped strand mat laminates exposed to H_2SO_4 (77%) after twelve months exposure at $40^\circ C$.

The presence of an applied load can significantly affect the environmental degradation. Pritchard and Taneja [3] have shown that the permeation of water through a GRP laminate is enhanced by an imposed strain greater than 0.3%. This increase in permeability may be attributed to enhanced diffusion through the matrix and to fibre debonding which would facilitate transport of the environment along the interface. Both these processes will lead to an increase in the degradation observed in immersion testing. In addition, it is possible that some failure processes occur under load that are quite distinct from the failure processes in immersion testing.

E-glass fibres are very susceptible to corrosion by mineral acids [4] which is associated with ion exchange reactions at the fibre surfaces. When the fibres are loaded, this corrosion may lead to catastrophic failure. In a composite, the resin matrix serves to protect the fibres from attack. However, if the acid can travel through the resin, either by diffusion or through microcracks, corrosion of the fibres may occur.

Published work on the stress corrosion of GRP is scarce [4-9]. However, many important parameters have been established. Collins [7] reported that stress corrosion is only a problem with solutions of $pH < 3$ to > 10 . All workers have discovered a marked dependence on the level of the applied load, and there is some evidence for a minimum strain below which stress corrosion does not occur.

The specific test details and conditions used in the experimental studies vary considerably. However, most of the tests in which microstructural detail of the fracture process have been studied have been performed on laminates with unidirectional layers of fibres oriented parallel to the imposed stress [4,7,8]. Under these conditions crack growth occurs perpendicular to the fibre direction. The cracks are usually very flat with only occasional steps.

The present work is an extension of an investigation [8] of the nucleation and propagation of stress corrosion cracks in hoop wound pipe sections to a similar study of pipe sections wound at $\pm 55^\circ$. The object of the work was to study the interaction between the damage processes which occur in the absence of a corrosive environment, primarily transverse cracking, and stress corrosion cracks which nucleate and grow at right angles to the fibre orientation. In addition it was hoped to establish that the detailed mechanisms found in hoop wound pipe could be extended to explain fracture under more complex loading conditions. In the tests on hoop wound pipe the material is subjected to a stress parallel to the fibre direction σ_{11} . The transverse stress σ_1 is negligible. In contrast, pipe sections with $\pm 55^\circ$ windings tested under the same loading conditions experience both longitudinal and transverse tensile stresses.

The first part of the paper summarises the main features of the results in hoop wound pipes which have been reported elsewhere [8] and outlines the mechanism of stress corrosion observed. The results of the $\pm 55^\circ$ pipe tests are then described and the mechanisms of crack nucleation and propagation discussed in terms of the effect of longitudinal and transverse stresses.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The pipe sections were made by filament winding using Fibreglass Suprewind E-glass fibre and a general purpose terephthalate polyester resin, Impol T500, made by I.C.I. Petrochemicals Division. Full details of the winding machine and the procedures involved have been given elsewhere [10]. The pipes were wound at a helix angle of $\pm 55^\circ$, and consisted of four laminae. The diameter of the pipes was 76 mm and the wall thickness varied between 1.7 and 2.0 mm. The pipes were given an initial cure on the forming mandrel and, after removal from the mandrel, a standard post cure of 3h at 80°C followed by 3h at 120°C . The fibre volume fraction was determined, using burn-off techniques to be 0.45.

Sections 75 mm long were cut from the pipes to form the test cylinders. For the stress corrosion tests the ends of the cylinders were sealed with sheets of transparent polyvinylidene chloride, using an epoxy resin. The acid environment was introduced into the sealed cylinder using a hypodermic syringe.

The loading conditions used in the stress corrosion tests are described in detail in [9]. The cylinders were subjected to diametrical compression between parallel plates, Fig.1. Both constant deflection and constant load conditions were used and failure was monitored continuously by recording the load reduction and the increase in deflection respectively with time. Calibration tests were made to determine the relation between the displacement $\Delta D/D$ and the maximum tensile strain ϵ_{max} at positions A and C.

Fig.1 Experimental arrangement for stress and strain corrosion tests on cylindrical sections.

The failure processes were examined using macrophotographic techniques and scanning electron microscopy. For the macrophotography, cracked sections were cut from the cylinders and photographed at low magnification using oblique lighting to highlight the cracks. Samples were cut from the failed sections using a jewellers saw and the fractured surfaces were sputtered with gold prior to examination in a Philips 501 scanning electron microscope.

STRESS CORROSION OF HOOP WOUND SECTIONS

When hoop wound sections are tested in air they fail by delamination and fibre fracture at displacements $\Delta D/D \approx 0.55$. Failure occurs at positions B and D (see Fig.1) by a combination of delamination and fibre fracture. A typical load relaxation curve for a section tested using 0.65 N HCl with $\Delta D/D = 0.13$ is shown in Fig.2. The fracture process can be divided into four stages as follows:-

Stage I is the initial viscoelastic response of the material to the applied load which is not affected by the environment used.

Stage II shows an approximately linear relaxation of load which is associated with slow deformation and microfracture. During this stage strain corrosion cracks are nucleated and grow slowly in position C. The number and distribution of the cracks depends on the initial displacement $\Delta D/D$, pipe section diameter D , wall thickness t , and the corrosive environment.

Stage III shows a sharp drop in load which is associated with the growth of large strain corrosion cracks and delaminations. The relaxation curves often show a series of steps indicating discontinuous growth of the cracks. Leakage occurs towards the end of Stage III.

Stage IV is a post strain corrosion failure region with a low relaxation rate. Crack nucleation occurs at the sides of the ring in regions B and D and leads to total collapse of the section by side failure.

Fig. 2 Typical load relaxation curve for a strain corrosion test.

Crack nuclei can be detected visually in Stage II and form at right angles to the fibre direction. They are characterised by very smooth, almost featureless, fracture surfaces with the plane of fracture of the fibres lying in the same plane as the fracture of the resin. A schematic representation of the progress of fracture is shown in Fig.3. As the crack grows the stress intensity at the crack tip increases and the fracture surface develops small steps parallel to the fibres due to delamination cracking. However, throughout crack growth the dominant feature is planar fracture at right angles to the fibre direction with a minimal amount of fibre pull-out. The effect of the acid is to reduce the strength of the fibre and it is the localised nature of the acid contact with the fibre, evident in Fig.3, which leads to the planar fracture characteristics.

Fig.3 Model of fracture processes in aligned GRP structures tested in corrosive environment, a) nucleation of first crack by acid attack on fibre, b) growth of flat crack by fibre fracture at tip of resin crack, c) development of small amount of pull-out due to out-of-plane fibre fracture d) delamination cracks at tip of flat crack.

The onset and progress of fracture is strongly dependent on the initial $\Delta D/D$, which in turn determines the maximum strain in region C. The failure times for tests in 0.65 N HCl are listed in Table 1.

ϵ_{max}	Time to fail (min)	
	Hoop	$\pm 55^\circ$
0.022	9	140
0.016	25	540
0.013	110	1,050
0.010	300	3,000
0.008	1,000	12,500
0.005	20,000	-

Table 1. Effect of initial ϵ_{max} (at C in Fig.1) on time to fail in 0.65 N HCl in constant load tests [9].

DRY TESTING OF $\pm 55^\circ$ PIPE SECTIONS

In contrast to the hoop pipe sections, the behaviour of $\pm 55^\circ$ pipe sections under parallel plate compression is characterised at low deformation by the formation of transverse cracks in the inner lamina at positions A and C. These cracks run along the fibre matrix interface parallel to the fibre direction and perpendicular to the inner surface. They start to form at deformations of the order of $\Delta D/D = 0.035$ ($\epsilon_{max} = 0.003$) and are spaced at regular intervals. The number of cracks increases as the deformation proceeds. At a later stage transverse cracks also occur in the outer lamina of the sections at B and D and in the second lamina at A and C. The transverse cracks at B and D may nucleate small unpeeling delaminations at the edges of the specimen.

The final failure of the pipe can occur in two ways depending upon the thickness to diameter ratio of the pipe sections (cf the behaviour of short beam shear test specimens). Thick walled specimens fail by a sudden massive delamination spreading from positions A and C towards B and D and extending across 25% of the pipe wall. Thin walled specimens fail by crushing at B and D. The crushed area consists of a jagged fibre fracture surrounded by localised delaminations. Most of the specimens used in the stress corrosion work would fail in air by massive delamination at $\Delta D/D = 52\%$.

GENERAL FEATURES OF STRESS CORROSION FAILURE OF $\pm 55^\circ$ PIPE SECTIONS

The shape of the load relaxation and displacement-time curves for strain and stress corrosion of $\pm 55^\circ$ pipe sections is very similar to the corresponding curves for hoop wound pipe (Fig.2). There are four distinct stages in the failure process, although some of the details are not the same as in hoop pipe sections. In Stage I the viscoelastic response is greater than for hoop wound sections and, in addition, transverse cracking of the inner layer may occur. The amount of transverse cracking depends on the value of the initial $\Delta D/D$. The transverse cracks are uniformly spaced. During Stage II $\Delta D/D$ increases slowly in constant load tests although the rate of increase is much greater in acid than for corresponding tests in air or water. The first evidence for stress corrosion cracks is the formation of small crack nuclei at right angles to the fibre direction. These cracks grow slowly during Stage II and are clearly visible to the naked eye towards the end of Stage II (Fig.4a). In Stage III the crack nuclei coalesce to form a single large crack which spreads through the wall of the section (Fig.4b) The crack nucleates delaminations as it grows and eventually causes leakage of the acid.

Fig.4 (a) Small stress corrosion cracks formed between large transverse cracks in early part of Stage II
 (b) Large stress corrosion cracks intersecting transverse cracks at beginning of Stage III

The ragged shape of the crack is due to the interaction between two types of cracking as illustrated schematically in Fig.5. The transverse cracks formed in Stage I divide the inner layer into parallel sided blocks. It will be shown later that these are subject to a longitudinal tensile stress. It is this stress which, in the presence of the acid, causes stress corrosion cracks to form at right

Fig. 5 Schematic representation of interaction between transverse and stress corrosion cracking.

angles to the fibres in an analogous way to the failure of hoop wound pipe. The stress corrosion cracks form along the line of maximum tensile stress at the bottom of the section and the zig-zag morphology develops. The macroscopic observations suggest that this process is repeated in subsequent layers and the detailed microstructural evidence is described in the next section. The appearance of the final fracture is shown in Fig. 6. Fracture after low initial loads is relatively smooth and the amount of transverse cracking is small. The dark diffuse band is due to delamination cracking. After high initial loads the fracture surface is very ragged and there is evidence of extensive transverse and delamination cracking.

Fig. 6 Appearance after complete fracture showing ragged crack morphology and delamination cracking.

As in hoop wound sections, the time to failure is strongly dependent on the initial $\Delta D/D$ and some typical results are given in Table 1. It will be noted that for a given ϵ_{\max} the failure times in $\pm 55^\circ$ sections are longer than in hoop sections.

DETAILS OF STRESS CORROSION CRACKING IN STAGES II AND III

The crack nuclei produced in Stage II are very similar in structure and morphology to the nuclei formed in hoop pipe fractures and consists of straight planar cracks cutting across the fibre direction. In the nucleation region the surface of the fracture is extremely smooth and almost featureless. In the hoop wound section tests the morphology gradually changes from the very smooth nucleation region, through regions of almost flat fracture containing secondary nucleation areas, to regions containing an increasing amount of out-of-plane failure. The final regions of fracture sometimes show fibre pull-out which is associated with conventional fracture of composite materials in the absence of corrosive environments.

These features are reproduced in the first, inner, lamina of the angle ply pipe fracture. A nucleation region is shown in Fig.7a between two transverse cracks and a higher magnification photograph of the nucleation site at N is shown in Fig.7b. By following the river line markings on the fibres and in the resin, it appears that nucleation has occurred a few fibre spacings below the free surface. The amount of out-of-plane fracture shown in Fig.7 increases away from the nucleation site. A special case showing more out-of-plane fracture is shown in Fig.8. Fracture occurred along the line of the fibre cross-over which is a feature of winding sequence used in this work as illustrated in Fig.9. Thus, for a $\pm 55^\circ$ winding, lines such as AB cross the fibres in lamina L-1 at an angle of 70° . The crack in Fig.8 has nucleated at the surface along a single transverse fibre belonging to lamina L-2 which is visible at P. The stepped geometry of the crack is presumably a result of the crack preferring to cross the fibres at right angles rather than at the 70° which is the orientation of the nucleation line. A higher magnification photograph of the stepped crack is shown in Fig.8b.

Fig. 7 (a) SEM photograph of nucleation regions.
(b) Higher magnification photograph of nucleation site N in (a).

Fig.8 (a) SEM photograph of out-of-plane stress corrosion crack. Path of fracture determined by adjacent lamina (see text and Fig.9).
 (b) Higher magnification photograph illustrating the stepped morphology.

Fig.9 Schematic representation of origin of out-of-plane fracture shown in Fig.8. (a) Cross-over sequence due to winding procedure. (b) Detail of roving interaction at cross-over point.

The fracture of the second lamina depends on the cracking processes in the first. Two possibilities have been identified. Firstly, growth of the stress corrosion crack in the first lamina can lead to delamination either at or near the second lamina. The acid can then reach a large surface of the second lamina and the processes of nucleation and growth of stress corrosion cracks at this lamina can occur. The second lamina may also fail by transverse cracking so that the fracture surface will have the ragged structure of the first lamina. Secondly, the presence of transverse cracks in the first lamina allows acid to reach the second lamina directly and again stress corrosion cracking can start in this lamina. These processes are evident in Fig.10. The transverse crack in the first lamina is shown at X. A stress corrosion crack has nucleated at the end of the transverse crack at Y and the characteristic flat fracture surfaces are produced, Fig.10b. As in the example shown in Figs. 8 and 9 the nucleation line defined by the end of the transverse crack is at 70° to the fibre direction in the second layer so that the stress corrosion crack has a stepped appearance with regions of 90° fracture joined by small cliffs. Many nucleation sites can be identified at the end of the transverse crack. Since most of the nucleation sites in the second lamina are

Fig.10 (a) SEM photograph of transverse and stress corrosion cracks.
 (b) Higher magnification photograph of region Y in (a).

associated with transverse cracks, it is likely that these nuclei form early in the failure process.

The complex interaction between transverse cracking, stress corrosion cracking and delamination cracking results in many different fracture surface geometries. A typical overview is shown in Fig.11.

Fig. 11 SEM photograph of a general view of final fracture.

DISCUSSION

The mechanism of stress and strain corrosion in $\pm 55^\circ$ angle ply sections appears to be the same as in hoop wound sections. However, there are several additional features of the failure process which result in different fracture surface morphologies and times to fail. In Stage I the initial viscoelastic response in the $\pm 55^\circ$ sections is much greater than in the hoop wound sections because a larger proportion of the load has to be taken by the resin. Similarly, during loading of the sections prior to introduction of the test liquid, the $\pm 55^\circ$ sections undergo transverse cracking, the amount of which depends on the initial load or displacement. The microscopic evidence indicates that the transverse cracks have a significant effect on the progress of crack growth because they allow the corrosive environment to come into contact with inner laminae which are oriented in different directions.

The longer failure times in $\pm 55^\circ$ sections compared with hoop wound sections for a given initial maximum strain (Table 1) can be attributed to differences in the tensile stress (σ_{II}) acting parallel to the fibre in the two sections. Similarly, transverse cracking in the $\pm 55^\circ$ sections must be due to a transverse stress (σ_I) generated by the imposed strain. The stress distribution in the ring at position C (Fig.1) will vary from a maximum tensile stress at the inside surface to a maximum compressive stress at the outside surface. For simplicity, it will be assumed that the inner lamina is subjected to a strain ϵ_{max} , i.e. the strain measured by a strain gauge on the inside surface. In this way the coupling forces between laminae and the strain distribution through the wall are ignored. For a hoop wound section, the stress parallel to the fibres is given by the simple rule of mixtures equation

$$\sigma_{II} = \epsilon_{max} V_f E_f + (1-V_f) E_m \quad (1)$$

where V_f is the volume fraction of fibres and E_f and E_m are the moduli of the fibres and matrix respectively.

Since $E_f \gg E_m$, at high V_f Eq.(1) reduces to

$$\sigma_{II} = \epsilon_{max} V_f E_f = \epsilon_{max} E_{II} \quad (2)$$

For $\pm 55^\circ$ sections the measured strain must first be expressed as a stress in the hoop direction (Fig.12).

$$\sigma_H = \epsilon_{\max} E_H \quad (3)$$

Using an experimentally determined value (10) for a pipe wound at $\pm 55^\circ$ $E_H = 0.56E$ gives

$$\sigma_H = 0.56 \epsilon_{\max} E_{||} \quad (4)$$

The stresses parallel and perpendicular to the fibres are obtained using the transformation equations

$$\sigma_{||} = 0.56 \epsilon_{\max} E_{||} \sin^2 55 = 0.375 \epsilon_{\max} E_{||} \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma_{\perp} = 0.56 \epsilon_{\max} E_{||} \cos^2 55 = 0.185 \epsilon_{\max} E_{||} \quad (6)$$

Fig. 12 Stresses and strains in test sections.

It follows that for a given ϵ_{\max} the effective stress $\sigma_{||}$ is less in a $\pm 55^\circ$ section than in a hoop section. Since the failure process in stress corrosion cracking involves fibre fracture, it is likely that the time to failure will be directly related to $\sigma_{||}$ as previously demonstrated for hoop wound sections. Thus, the $\pm 55^\circ$ sections should have longer times to failure than hoop wound sections as shown in Table 1. When the data in Table 1 is normalised to predict the failure times at a constant value of $\sigma_{||}$ for hoop wound and $\pm 55^\circ$ sections, it is found that $\pm 55^\circ$ sections fail before the hoop wound sections (Table 2). This can be explained in terms of the transverse cracking processes which occur in the $\pm 55^\circ$ sections. Experimentally determined values for the critical transverse cracking stress σ_{\perp}^* and $E_{||}$ are 18.6 MNm^{-2} and 40.2 GNm^{-2} respectively. Thus from Eq.(6) transverse cracking will occur for all values of $\epsilon_{\max} > 0.0025$. In the present experiments the minimum value of ϵ_{\max} was 0.005 (Table 1). The transverse cracks will lead to a stress magnification at the second layer and this, in the presence of the corrosive environment, will result in an enhanced stress cracking effect.

$\frac{\sigma_{ }}{E_{ }}$	Time to fail (min)	
	Hoop	$\pm 55^{\circ}$
0.022	9	-
0.016	25	-
0.013	110	-
0.010	300	50
0.008	1,000	150
0.005	20,000	1,150

Table 2. Effect of initial $\sigma_{||}$ (at C in Fig. 1) on time to fail in 0.65 N HCl in constant load tests.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The mechanism of stress and strain corrosion in $\pm 55^{\circ}$ angle ply sections is the same as in hoop wound sections [8].
2. Transverse cracks have a significant effect on the overall fracture process because they allow the corrosive environment to penetrate through the pipe wall.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are grateful to the Science Research Council for financial support and to their colleagues without whose help this work could not have been done.

REFERENCES

1. ASHBEE, K.H.G. and WYATT, R.C., Proc. Roy. Soc., Series A, Vol.312, 1969,p.553.
2. NORWOOD, L.S. and FAIRBROTHER, T., Symposium on Reinforced Plastics in Anti-Corrosion Applications, Paper No.8, N.E.L., East Kilbride, 1979.
3. PRITCHARD, G. and TANEJA, N., Composites 4, 1973, p. 181.
4. BARKER, H.A., BAIRD-SMITH, I.G. and JONES, F., Symposium on Reinforced Plastics in Anti-Corrosion Applications, Paper No.12, N.E.L., East Kilbride, 1979.
5. ROBERTS, R.C., Reinforced Plastics Congress, British Plastics Federation, Paper No.19, Brighton, 1978.
6. TORP, S. and ARVESEN, R., Proc. 34th Ann. Conf., S.P.I. Reinforced Plastics Composites Institute, Paper 13-D, New Orleans, 1979.
7. COLLINS, H.H., Plastics and Rubber : Materials and Applications, 3, 1978, p.6.
8. HOGG, P.J. and HULL, D., (to be published in 'Micromechanisms of Crack Extension', Metals Society, London).
9. HOGG, P.J., SPENCER, B. and HULL, D. (to be published).
10. HULL, D., LEGG, M.J. and SPENCER, B., Composites, 9, 1978, 17.